

Welcome to the DATAMITE Newsletter

Our motto: Unleashing the Monetisation Potential of Data.

2025: a year of remarkable achievements

By Santiago Cáceres, DATAMITE Project Coordinator

As we approach the conclusion of the **DATAMITE** project, 2025 has been a year of remarkable achievements. We **successfully finalised the DATAMITE Framework**, a cornerstone for data monetisation, and developed key assets, including the Data Maturity Model and the Valuation Model, among others. These deliverables represent significant progress toward empowering organisations to unlock the full potential of their data. Alongside these technical milestones, we have invested

heavily in dissemination and communication, including an **ongoing series of webinars** designed to share knowledge and foster collaboration across the European data community.

As we move into the final phase, **our wish list for 2026 is ambitious**: we aim to demonstrate the full potential of **DATAMITE** through six real-world pilot demonstrators, continue our successful webinar series, and refine strategies for exploitation to ensure long-term impact. We warmly invite you to join our upcoming webinars and explore the recordings on [our YouTube channel](#). Don't miss the chance to see how **DATAMITE** is shaping the future of data-driven innovation.

And finally, we're sending our best wishes for a joyful holiday season and a data-driven New Year!

Webinar series - Unlocking Data Value with DATAMITE!

We are launching a new series of webinars to showcase the work carried out at DATAMITE over the last years. The following webinars are already available:

Unlocking Open Source Potential: DATAMITE's open source guide and how you can contribute to it

The banner features a dark blue background with a pattern of white dots at the bottom. On the right, there is a glowing padlock icon set against a background of circuitry. A red YouTube play button is overlaid on the text. The text on the left reads: 'UNLOCKING DATA VALUE WITH DATAMITE WEBINAR SERIES' followed by 'UNLOCKING OPEN SOURCE POTENTIAL: DATAMITE'S OPEN SOURCE GUIDE AND HOW YOU CAN CONTRIBUTE TO'. At the bottom right, there is a white play button icon, a person icon, the text 'ECLIPSE', a calendar icon, the date '27 NOVEMBER 2025' and time '11:00 - 12:00 CET', a location pin icon, and the text 'ONLINE'.

On 27 November, David Remón from [Eclipse Foundation](#) delivered the fourth webinar in our 'Unlocking Data Value with DATAMITE' series, exploring data monetisation.

Creating data products from scratch with DATAMITE

UNLOCKING DATA VALUE WITH DATAMITE
WEBINAR SERIES

CREATING DATA PRODUCTS FROM SCRATCH WITH DATAMITE

11 DECEMBER 2025
11:00 - 12:00 CET
ONLINE

ITI

The banner features a dark blue background with a pattern of white dots. On the right, there is a 3D visualization of data clouds and charts. A red play button is centered over the main title. At the bottom, there are icons for a person, a calendar, and a location pin, along with the text 'ITI', '11 DECEMBER 2025 11:00 - 12:00 CET', and 'ONLINE'.

On 11 December, Jordi Arjona from [ITI](#) delivered the fifth webinar in our 'Unlocking Data Value with DATAMITE' series, exploring data monetisation.

DATAMITE from a business point of view

Designed with real market needs in mind, DATAMITE enables companies to unlock the value of their data. It provides tailored monetisation strategies, open-source tools and actionable business models to achieve this. In the 'DATAMITE from a business point of view' video series, we explore how DATAMITE facilitates fair data valuation, generates new business opportunities and establishes a foundation for the sustainable exploitation of data across European industries. To this end, we interviewed four partners responsible for some of DATAMITE's use cases.

María José López from Tecnalia

We interview María José López from [TecNALIA](#), a key partner in the development of the DATAMITE framework. For TecNALIA, as a research centre, the experience and knowledge acquired from working on this project would be valuable for continuing to work in the fields of data quality and governance, building on these outcomes to generate more valuable findings.

EVENTS

DATAMITE at EBDVF 2025

The [European Big Data Value Forum \(EBDVF\) 2025](#) took place from 12 to 14 November in Copenhagen, Denmark. The event, organised by the [Big Data](#)

[Value Association \(BDVA\)](#), brought together industry professionals, business developers, researchers and policy-makers from all over Europe and other regions of the world to **advance policy actions and industrial and research activities** in the areas of Data and AI.

As with previous editions in [2023](#) and [2024](#), **DATAMITE did not want to miss this important event**. A large delegation from the project travelled to Copenhagen to represent the consortium at various activities spread over the three days of the forum: the **project had a booth**, it **hosted a dedicated DATAMITE session**, and **DATAMITE participated in the EUDATA+ cluster session**.

[Discover more](#)

VIDEO: DATAMITE at EBDVF | Recap of the EUDATA+ session

On 13 November, **DATAMITE had the pleasure of co-hosting a session and co-running a booth as part of the EUDATA+ cluster**. The EUDATA+ session, “A Journey Through the Data Lifecycle – Innovations, Use Cases, Values”, explored how data creates value, from its acquisition and enrichment to its real-world impact.

We are very happy to share a **video prepared by** our communication and dissemination partner, [AUSTRALO](#), **showcasing the session's highlights** and featuring interviews with the people who made it possible.

DATAMITE at Infocom World 2025

The [Infocom World Conference 2025](#) took place on 26 November, combining an online event with an in-person gathering in Athens, under the theme '**AI-Volution: A Brave New World!**'. The annual meeting explored how AI and emerging technologies are transforming the business landscape, bringing together top decision-makers, ICT leaders and investors who are shaping the future.

[As in 2024](#), **DATAMITE** was present at InfoCom 2025 in two ways.

[Discover more](#)

DATAMITE plenary meeting in Valencia

From 29 to 30 October, the DATAMITE consortium held its final plenary meeting of 2025 in Valencia, Spain. This important meeting was held to **discuss the steps needed to achieve the project's goal** before DATAMITE ends, following the grant of an extension. As at the previous [plenary meetings in Aachen](#) and [in Bilbao](#), the agenda included a CodeCamp day with the project's developers on the first day, followed by two days with the entire consortium. Each work package presented its progress and future steps.

Hosted by ITI ([Instituto Tecnológico de la Informática](#)), the two-day plenary meeting focused on **reviewing project progress, strengthening collaboration, and coordinating upcoming work phases**.

[Discover more](#)

DELIVERABLES

D4.6 - Legal and Ethical Guidelines on Data Transfers and Trading

D4.6 constitutes both a revision and an elaboration of D4.5. The current text is thus not only preoccupied with excelling at presenting and analysing the principles touched upon in the previous Deliverable, but also with exploring additional topics, e.g. sectoral aspects, the role of data spaces, etc. D4.6 is of its kind also a review of the DATAMITE's Pilots, in the context of these topics.

[Read it here](#)

D4.7 - LLM-based Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) System for Identifying Effective Data Monetisation Strategies

This deliverable builds upon the data valuation framework and decision-support tools previously developed within WP4 of the DATAMITE project, extending them through the integration of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) techniques.

[Read it here](#)

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